

ANALYSIS OF PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION IN EDUCATION UNITS IN CAMPO GRANDE - MS

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7411374

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ABSTRACT

Currently, domestic photovoltaic systems are cost-competitive with the conventional grid of fossil fuels and hydroelectric energy sources, both from an environmental and financial point of view. However, to satisfy the basic need of the consumer and the improvements in alternative energy technologies, the energy system provided by hydroelectric plants is still easier to obtain. For the feasibility study proposed in this study, we have that it will seek to achieve favorable results for the installation of a photovoltaic system in a public school, where the financial return should be considerably favorable to such adoption. Thus, it is necessary to further promote this technological innovation of clean energy generation, so that it can reach levels of satisfaction and recognition of the population, so that its dissemination becomes increasingly broad within the clean energy market.

Keywords: Energy. photovoltaic. Solar. Panel. System .

1. INTRODUCTION

Most human activities depend directly on the use of energy and, although the Brazilian model, highly dependent on hydroelectric power plants, is relatively “less polluting” and renewable in relation to other energy sources, it still needs non-renewable sources such as electricity. oil or coal burning, which is subject to shortages, and which may compromise the country's energy supply.

Bearing in mind that the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), proposed by the United Nations (UN) in the 2030 Agenda, “are a global call to action to end poverty, protect

the environment and climate, and ensure that people everywhere can enjoy peace and prosperity” (UN, 2021).

In terms of sustainability, nothing better than this energy, with a generation potential far greater than human consumption. In this way, the implementation of photovoltaic generation can be a technically and economically viable alternative in municipal public buildings, which have high expenses with electricity bills. The hypothesis to be confirmed is whether it would be feasible to implement individual photovoltaic microgeneration units in municipal public schools.

2. DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Electricity production and costs

The production of electricity through hydroelectric plants covers 65.2% of the sources, according to the Energy Research Company (2020). There are other forms of energy generation that are not so predominant, such as biomass, wind, solar, natural gas, burning coal and oil products, and nuclear.

For this, there is a commercial cost of using these distribution networks. In Brazil, the electricity tariff is defined by the National Electric Energy Agency (ANEEL), the body that establishes the amount to be paid by final consumers of electricity.

Usually, tariffs can be calculated via the distribution concessionaire (distributor) and via the transmission concessionaire (transmitter) which, respectively, have tariffs named tariff for the use of electrical distribution systems (TUSD) and tariff for the use of electrical distribution systems. transmission (TUST). They are tariff sub-components whose nature helps to understand the composition of the TE.

While TUSD and TUST tariffs are quite stable, some variables such as weather or drought which affect energy production are reflected in the price. Other variables are related to consumption and the socioeconomic status of the residence. Currently, there are the following types of flags, they are:

Green Flag	Favorable generation conditions	no additional cost
Yellow Flag	less favorable conditions	BRL 2,989 for every 100 kilowatt-hours (kWh) consumed
Red Flag 1	unfavorable conditions	BRL 6,500 for every 100 kWh consumed

Red Flag 2	very unfavorable conditions	BRL 9.795 for every 100 kWh consumed
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Table 1– Types of electricity consumption flags in Brazil

Source: ANEEL (2022)

Understanding how tariffs and energy is produced will help in understanding the implementation process and the advantages of installing micro photovoltaic plants in public schools. Thus, it is necessary to understand the binomial tariff and the internal rate of return of producers/consumers.

2.2. Legislation

Law 10,848/2004 establishes rules for the sale of electricity between concessionaires, permit holders and authorized service providers and electric power installations, as well as between these and their consumers. Mainly the hiring, by energy distributors, of the entire market for energy from distributed generation (SOLFÁCIL, 2022).

Already Decree n. 5,163/2004 regulates the commercialization of electric energy, the process of granting concessions and authorizations for the generation of electric energy. Changes some points of the previous law and takes measures, such as the mention of the DG contracting model by concessionaires (SOLFÁCIL, 2022).

One of the most important was ANEEL Normative 482/2012, whose guidelines guided the exponential growth of distributed microgeneration and minigeneration. It was the regulatory framework that allowed consumers to exchange generated energy with that of the electrical network, creating the rules and the system that compensates the consumer for the electrical energy injected into the network. That is, it establishes the general conditions for access by microgeneration and distributed minigeneration to electricity distribution systems, the electricity compensation system.

Law no. 14,300/2022 Legal Framework for Distributed Microgeneration and Minigeneration. The law regulates the generation modalities, the Electric Energy Compensation System (SCEE) and the Social Renewable Energy Program (PERS). It was already gaining the support of companies operating in the Distributed Generation sector for providing legal certainty to activities hitherto regulated by ANEEL normative resolutions.

It should be noted that the law in question did not revoke ANEEL Normative Resolution n. 482/2012, however the law prevails under the regulations. That is, in case of disagreement, the decision of the law annuls the regulation.

All legislative and regulatory changes in solar energy contribute significantly to this work, since it is necessary to understand the demands that involve the process of implantation of micro plants in the school environment.

And, even with such changes, a requirement remained, due to its constituent nature: no purchase, alienation, service and work, in public space or property, can occur without bidding.

2.3. Ways to obtain solar energy

The two fundamental methods of capturing energy from the sun, heat and photoreaction, can also be combined in various ways to provide combined energy carriers such as heat and electricity. Thus, from the two basic ways of capturing the sun's energy, in addition to daylight, i.e. heat and photoreaction, we distinguish four main application domains: photovoltaic electricity, heating, solar thermal electricity, and solar fuel manufacturing. (MASTER DISTANCE, 2009).

2.4. Production of photovoltaic energy

Photovoltaic energy is the conversion of light into electricity, using semiconductor materials that realize the photovoltaic effect, a phenomenon studied in physics, photochemistry and electrochemistry. A photovoltaic system employs solar panels, usually made of silicon, each comprising a number of solar cells, which generate electrical energy. (AUDIBERT; ROUARD, 1979).

2.5. photovoltaic energy storage

Electricity storage systems that are available on the market are suitable for use in retrofitting existing photovoltaic installations and can also be included in the system design when planning new installations. All storage systems save excess energy and make it available at a later time (SOUZA, 1994).

2.6. Types of photovoltaic systems

The current commercial photovoltaic technology is crystalline silicon. Monocrystalline or multicrystalline crystalline silicon technologies currently dominate the market with an 85% share. Cells are cut from ingots or castings, or made from grown strands of highly purified silicon. A potential junction is created, an anti-reflective coating deposited, and metal contacts added. The cells are then grouped into modules with clear glass to the front, weatherproof

material to the back, and often a frame around it. The back can also be made of glass to allow the passage of light (DOLIF; SILVEIRA; GOMES, 2009).

2.7. Technological innovations for photovoltaic energy

While the growth of research in the field of photovoltaics and the improvement of currently existing technologies has proven to be efficient, the urgency of mitigating climate change means that there is no time to wait for the next generation of technology before rapidly expanding solar generation (ALMONDES, 2015).

Thus, current research focuses on technologies from a wide range of time horizons, from today's commercial technologies to long-term, high-risk transformational approaches, in all cases investigating ways to become the most advanced solar energy technologies. cheaper to manufacture, easier to deploy and more energy efficient than those currently available on the market (CABELLO; POMPERMAYER, 2013).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the development of the photovoltaic plant that will be installed at the school, it was selected to be installed in the state of Mato Grosso Sul, in an area operated by the ENERGISA concessionaire, in accordance with the determinations of ANEEL resolution No. 482/2021.

Thus, in order to obtain the average generation value that must be adopted for sizing the system, Table 1 lists the consumption history of the consumer unit within the year 2021.

months	Consumption (MWh)
January	211
February	209
March	202
April	178
May	170
June	169
July	182
August	199
September	179
October	200
November	187
December	192

Total	2278
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Table 1- Consumption history for the year 2021

Source: From the author himself (2022)

Within the choice of the region where the plants will be installed, the region that presents a great reception of solar radiation must be taken into account. Thus, within Mato Grosso do Sul and, at the same time, within ENERGISA's concession areas, the region selected for the installation of the plants is the municipality of Campo Grande.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the photovoltaic power generation system dimensioned here, string inverters whose model is SG250HX, produced by the company SunGrow, will be used. This is because such inverters are able to meet the input and output voltage requirements demanded by the photovoltaic system dimensioned here. The power of such inverters is 250.00 KWac, where their technical specifications can be seen in Table 2.

Input data	
MPPT Voltage Range	860V - 1300V
MPPT Entry Numbers	two
Maximum DC Voltage (Vdc)	1500V
Output Data	
AC Rated Power	250 kW
Maximum AC Current	180.5 A
Nominal AC Voltage	800V
Nominal AC Frequency	50/60 Hz
Total Harmonic Distortion (THD)	< 3%
Power factor	Adjustable
Maximum Efficiency	0.99

Table 2 – Technical specifications of bifacial photovoltaic panels

Source: From the author himself (2022)

As previously specified, the photovoltaic system in question must have a generation of 2,278 MWh, with a minimum supply of 95% of that established average value. Considering the high irradiation in the region, the Capacity Factor (FC) that the system can have is 16.8%,

according to data consulted with SolarGIS (2022). Allied to this, the use of the tracker in the system will provide an increase in energy generation in the photovoltaic system, which, according to NREL (2018), is around 20%. Therefore, a FC of 20.18% can be adopted for the system using the tracker.

According to the calculations carried out, the short-circuit current becomes possible with the use of 42 strings and the current for the maximum voltage for 23 strings. Therefore, the lowest value should be adopted, which would be 23 strings in parallel, because according to the I x V curve (for a current above 13.54 A), the current will be maintained at this value and would not be generating the ideal power. As a result, there will be a loss of power generation.

Therefore, we have a quantity of 4 inverters so that the quantity of 78 strings is supported by the photovoltaic generation system. Once the number of modules to be used for the photovoltaic generation system has been defined, their arrangement must satisfy a provision that allows the use of a solar radiation tracking system, where it will be carried out through the use of trackers.

Depending on the chosen model, it allows the movement of the modules on two tables connected directly to a mechanical axis responsible for the movement of the system. According to the aforementioned manufacturer's specification, the distance between the motor and the drive shaft is 6 m, where such distance can be adopted according to the need to avoid possible shading on the panels. This variation, according to the supplier, must be limited to 0.5 m. Considering all the calculations performed previously, the preliminary surveys of the system can be summarized in Table 3.

Total System Power [kWp]	1181.52
Minimum number of modules	2188
Minimum Number of Strings	78
Number of Tables	40
Number of Trackers	20
Number of Inverters	4
Installed Capacity [kWac]	1000

Table 3 - Photovoltaic system sizing data
Source: From the author himself (2022)

Within a sizing process for a photovoltaic energy generation system, the use of computational tools proves to be feasible to better parameterize the system in question. Thus,

within the sizing to be carried out within this study, the Pvsyst software will be used, where it is widely used within the minigeneration demands and has its design made by the University of Geneva, Switzerland.

In this way, the pilot project, which will guide future bids, in order to meet the entire demand of the Municipality of Campo Grande, will include the Municipal Education Department - SEMED, which has an average monthly consumption of 956,536.90 kWh.

Being implemented in 254 consumer units out of a total of 613. Studies will be carried out for each unit, with the survey of consumption data based on the year 2019, in view of the interference, with reduced consumption, caused by the closure of many units due to the COVID-19 pandemic (SEGES, 2021).

The implementation of this system will have approximately 17,382 photovoltaic modules, which after implementation in the 254 units of SEMED, will have an energy generation of approximately 961,775.02 kWh, as shown in Table 3.

Modules	17,382
configured area	49,712.52 m ²
configured power	7,126.62 kWp
average annual generation	11,541,300.36 kWh
average monthly generation	961,775.02 kWh
Average monthly consumption	950,745 kWh
Average kWh cost	BRL 0.98
kWh / module	54.7
CO ₂ emissions avoided	326,196,557 kg CO ₂ /year

Table 4 - Data on consumer units to be implemented in photovoltaic plants in Campo Grande-MS.

Source: Municipal Department of Management of Campo Grande - SEGES

The estimated cost for implementing the system is approximately 26 million Reais, which, considering the various units where they will be implemented, can be dismembered and auctioned by consumer unit, encouraging local entrepreneurs in the photovoltaic energy market, so that small regional companies come to answer the public notice call, providing the

installation of the system. In this way, the project will be able to provide local economic and social development, further stimulating the market for micro and mini-generation of photovoltaic energy.

5. EXPECTED RESULTS

In order to make comparisons, it will first be necessary to dimension the plants that would be placed in a concession area by a municipal school that has a good level of solar irradiation. With this, the aim is to obtain calculations to adapt the software simulations so that the energy generated is as close as possible to the consumption of the customer in question.

This article also presents a position, of the potential that the generation of photovoltaic energy, by the public power, has as an inducing tool and promoter of the sustainable development objectives of the 2030 Agenda in the city of Campo Grande - MS, if public procurement procedures are adopted with a view to local development and sustainability.

With the simulations in PVSyst, it is intended to identify some peculiarities that differed between the plants at the time of the simulation, such as orientation, since a plant is composed of a tracker structure, it has more orientations than the other, which was fixed. Therefore, it is intended to demonstrate that the bifacial module, together with the tracker system, can be a viable option for the generation of photovoltaic energy by the studied school.

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THANKS

This work was carried out with support from the Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul – UFMS/MEC – Brazil and the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel – Brazil (Capes) – Financing Code 001.